

Accuracy of Cipher Classification for Different Encryption Methods Versus Inclusion of Different Byte-Level Features

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Abstract:

Modern encryption algorithms such as AES and DES are designed to produce ciphertext outputs that appear statistically indistinguishable from noise. Assembled into random characters, encrypted text functions to mask patterns and resist statistical analysis. This study aims to investigate whether statistical features extracted from ciphertext chunks can be used to retrace which encryption algorithm was used, and specifically how the inclusion or exclusion of certain statistical features affects classification accuracy. We encrypted four literary texts using three cipher configurations, including AES-CBC, AES-ECB, and DES-ECB. Using these, ten features from 128-byte ciphertext chunks were extracted. We trained a Random Forest classifier on these features and used an analysis in which each feature was systematically removed to measure its contribution to overall accuracy. Our results indicate that three-way classification (AES-CBC vs. AES-ECB vs. DES-ECB) achieves 61.9% accuracy compared to a 33.3% baseline, while two-way classification (AES vs. DES) achieves a 92.8% accuracy. The large accuracy gap between the two tests suggests that choosing between two encryption algorithms leaves stronger statistical differences in ciphertext than choosing between two modes of the same algorithm (CBC vs. ECB). Mean byte value and maximum byte frequency are the most important features, while some top byte frequency features appear to contribute noise, though inconsistently. McNemar's test did not confirm statistical significance for any individual feature removal (all $p > 0.05$), perhaps due to the limited test set size ($n = 48$). Our results demonstrate that encryption algorithms leave detectable statistical fingerprints, and that feature selection can allow us to exploit those differences.

Introduction:

One of the most fascinating concepts in computer science and cybersecurity today is encryption, specifically if something designed to be random can leave traces of structure. Modern encryption is built on the idea that data should resemble random output that is uniformly convoluted and indistinguishable from noise [5]. The two most widely known modern symmetric encryption algorithms are the Advanced Encryption Standard (AES) and the Data Encryption Standard (DES), both block ciphers that use identical keys for encryption and decryption. AES, adopted as the modern standard in 2001, uses a 128-bit key and 16-byte block size, while its predecessor DES uses a 64-bit key and 8-byte block size. The question becomes, how is it possible that machine learning models can still detect which method of encryption was used?

Most analysts try to break the content of the message, the “what”. Analyzing the format of the message is arguably just as essential. If it’s known that the data was encrypted using a specific algorithm, that knowledge alone can inform further analysis and security decisions. Recent studies suggest that even encrypted data retains statistical signatures that can be analyzed using entropy and byte frequency distributions [1,2]. Encryption is a series of mathematical computations that retain their underlying behavior, generating an astronomically large 2^{128} and 2^{64} possible keys respectively. An interesting tension emerges: the closer encryption gets to perfect randomness, the less distinguishable the system itself becomes.

This study asks and aims to answer two primary research questions. First, can byte-level statistical features extracted from fixed ciphertext chunks classify which algorithm produced them? Second, how does the inclusion or exclusion of individual features affect that classification accuracy; that is, which features are useful and which generate noise. In network security, digital forensics, and other sectors of cybersecurity, identifying which encryption method was used can result in vastly different approaches. Identifying that a weak or outdated cipher was used, for instance, might lead to a faster breakthrough.

This is a supervised classification problem, meaning that the model learns from labeled chunks of ciphertext (each tagged with the cipher that produced it), and predicts the label for unseen chunks. The input data is numerical, specifically ten statistical features computed from the raw bytes of each ciphertext chunk, derived from literary texts. The output is a label identifying one of three cipher configurations: AES-CBC, AES-ECB, and DES-ECB. We also tested a simplified two-way version of this exact task, which only classifies between AES and DES regardless of the mode. Our hypothesis is that algorithm-level differences between AES and DES will be easier to detect than mode-level differences within the same algorithm, due to structural differences between both ciphers.

Background:

The task of identifying encryption algorithms from ciphertext alone has been explored already in prior academic works using both statistical and machine learning methods. Two studies are especially relevant to our work.

Mallikarjuna et al. [1] used machine learning to classify four symmetric encryption algorithms (AES, DES, RC2, and CAST) across four different cipher modes using features like Hamming weight distributions, ciphertext length, and entropy. They tested multiple classifiers and achieved a best accuracy of 71.0% using XGBoost (Extreme Gradient Boosting). They also found that ECB mode was the easiest to classify because identical plaintext blocks make identical ciphertext blocks, while CBC and other modes introduced excess randomness that made

classification very difficult. This is consistent with our hypothesis, described in *Introduction*, that mode-level differences are harder to detect than broader algorithmic differences.

Ithape and Purushothama [2] tested deep neural networks, Random Forest, and logistic regression on AES and DES across ECB, CBC, CFB, and CTR modes. Their best result was 70% accuracy using a deep neural network, and Random Forest achieved 68%. They found that statistical methods alone were limited to ECB mode and that machine learning models considerably outperformed them across all modes. A strength of their study is that it tested multiple model types and compared them directly, although it did not investigate which specific features affected this accuracy.

Our study differs from both in important ways. First, we investigate exactly which features affect accuracy and to what extent they can be attributed to increases or decreases in accuracy. Second, we apply McNemar's test (a statistical analysis that determines how significant percentage differences are) to assess whether observed accuracy differences are statistically significant. This adds insight to the foundational results of previous studies.

Dataset:

Our dataset consists of numerical data derived from the four encrypted literary texts used. The source material is the plaintext language data in English, which is processed into 128-byte vectors for use in the classifier model. The four source texts we used are:

- Alice's Adventures in Wonderland* by Lewis Carroll (Project Gutenberg [9], ~170KB)
- The Art of War* by Sun Tzu, translated from Classical Chinese (Project Gutenberg [10], ~334KB)
- The Time Machine* by H.G. Wells (Project Gutenberg [11], ~200KB)
- Harry Potter and the Half-Blood Prince* by J.K. Rowling [12] (~6MB)

These literary texts were selected to represent diverse writing styles, genres, and original languages. The diversity helps reduce the likelihood of bias towards the specificities of a single text's character distribution. The first novel is the simplest, while the second novel is more complex; by varying lengths and complexities of our dataset, we can limit bias. All four texts were used for perplexity testing, but only *Alice's Adventures in Wonderland* was used in the feature analysis.

Each text was encrypted using the pycryptodome library: AES in Cipher Block Chaining mode (AES-CBC) with a 128-bit key and 16-byte block size; AES in Electronic Codebook mode (AES-ECB) with a 128-bit key and 16-byte block size; and DES in Electronic Codebook mode (DES-ECB) with a 64-bit key and 8-byte block size. Key size is fixed across all tests. The

Carroll text was cut into 80 chunks, each 128 bytes long. Each chunk was encrypted under all three cipher configurations, which produced 80 labeled samples per encryption method and 240 total samples. Carroll was used as the primary text for classifier training because it provided a sufficient chunk count for the 80/20 split. The dataset was split 80/20 into training (192 samples) and testing (48 samples) sets using a fixed random seed (`random_state=42`) to ensure identical test samples across comparisons.

From each encrypted chunk, ten features were extracted to form the input for the classifier. These features capture different statistical properties of the bytes inside each chunk and are described in Table 1. Entropy is a measure of how random the byte distribution is, and a perfectly encrypted chunk should approach 8 bits. Mean is the average byte value, which should be near 127.5 for random data. Variance measures how spread out each byte value is, which differs between AES and DES because of their different block sizes. Max frequency measures how often the most common byte appears, which can reveal patterns. Unique ratio measures how many of the 256 byte combinations appear in the chunk of data. Finally, the top-5 frequency features capture the five most common byte values, which could reveal structural differences between ciphers. Together, these ten features give the classifier a solid numerical description of each encrypted chunk.

Index	Feature Name	Description
0	Entropy	Randomness of the byte distribution
1	Mean	Average byte value (0–255)
2	Variance	Spread of byte values around the mean
3	Max Frequency	Proportion of the most common byte value
4	Unique Ratio	Proportion of distinct byte values out of 256
5	Top-5 Freq. 1	Highest normalized byte frequency
6	Top-5 Freq. 2	Second highest normalized byte frequency
7	Top-5 Freq. 3	Third highest normalized byte frequency

8	Top-5 Freq. 4	Fourth highest normalized byte frequency
9	Top-5 Freq. 5	Fifth highest normalized byte frequency

Table 1. The ten features are extracted from each 128-byte ciphertext chunk, used as input to the classifier.

Methodology:

Our study uses a supervised classification approach; the model learns from labeled examples and tries to predict labels for new chunks it hasn't seen before. The goal is to train a model that takes the features extracted from a ciphertext chunk and predicts which of three cipher configurations produced it: AES-CBC, AES-ECB, or DES-ECB. We also test a two-way version of this task, classifying only between AES and DES encryptions regardless of mode.

We use a Random Forest classifier, which is implemented using the scikit-learn library's RandomForestClassifier. Random Forest classifiers work by building a large number of decision trees, each trained on a random subset of data and features. Each tree makes a prediction, and the final output is determined by the majority vote out of each tree. This approach is more reliable because single decision trees tend to overfit (memorize patterns), but averaging across many trees reduces this problem. We set `n_estimators=500`, meaning the model builds 500 decision trees. The model takes in the ten features described in *Dataset* and outputs one of three labels.

We selected Random Forest over other classifiers such as Logistic Regression and Support Vector Machines for several reasons. Random Forest handles small datasets well and is resistant to overfitting because it averages across many trees. It also provides built-in feature importance scores, which directly support our research question about which features contribute most to classification accuracy. The hyper parameter we set was `n_estimators`, the number of decision trees. The `random_state` was fixed at 42 for all experiments to ensure reproducibility.

The dataset of 240 samples was split into 192 training samples and 48 testing samples, the latter used to evaluate accuracy. This same split was used consistently across experiments so that all model comparisons were made on identical test samples. For the three-way task, the baseline accuracy (based on a random pick) is 33.3%. For the two-way task, the baseline accuracy is 50.0%. To investigate how each individual feature affects overall accuracy, we conducted a method known as leave-one-feature-out (LOFO); a technique in machine learning used to

determine feature importance or select optimal features for a predictive model. Each of the ten features was removed one at a time and the classifier was trained on the remaining 9 features, yielding varying accuracy numbers. The change in accuracy compared to the full ten-feature baseline helps identify whether each feature helps or hurts the classifier, and to what extent.

To assess the statistical significance of each accuracy result, we applied McNemar’s test. McNemar’s test is a statistical test designed to compare two different classifiers on the same set of test samples. It looks at the specific samples where the models disagree and if those differences were real or based on random chance. It works by counting b , the number of samples the full model got right but the reduced model got wrong, and c , the number the reduced model got right but the full model got wrong. If b and c are very different, the test concludes the two models perform significantly differently. We considered $p < 0.05$ as the threshold for statistical significance.

Figure 1. Random Forest feature importance scores. Higher scores indicate features the model relied on more heavily.

Figure 2. Illustration of the leave-one-feature-out procedure. Green bars indicate noise features, red bars indicate useful features.

Results:

Our Random Forest classifier trained on ten features achieved a maximum of 61.9% accuracy on the three-way classification task we assigned (AES-CBC vs. AES-ECB vs. DES-ECB), compared to the random baseline of 33.3%. This represents a substantial improvement over random chance, almost doubling our baseline. For the two-way classification (AES vs. DES), accuracy reached a maximum of 92.8%, compared to a 50.0% baseline. A three-way classification using solely basic features (entropy, mean, variance) was also tested. Table 2 summarizes these results best.

Classification Task	Random Baseline	Accuracy	Improvement
3-way full comp.	33.3%	61.9%	+28.6 pp
2-way full comp.	50.0%	92.8%	+42.8 pp
3-way basic comp.	33.3%	38.5%	+5.2 pp

Table 2. Classification accuracy for all three experiments. "pp" = percentage points above the random baseline. All results use a Random Forest classifier with 500 decision trees.

The large gap between the three-way full result (61.9%) and the two-way result (92.8%) is the most significant finding of this study. This can be attributed to the structural differences between AES and DES, as AES uses a 16-byte block size while DES uses an 8-byte block size. When the 128-byte chunk of text is encrypted, AES produces 8 independent blocks while DES produces 16. The difference in block division leads to some distinguishability between both encryption methods. AES-CBC and AES-ECB, by contrast, share a very similar structure with the same cipher and block size, making their outputs harder to separate with features alone.

Our testing of the basic feature set using only entropy, mean, and variance only achieved 38.5% accuracy on the three-way task, barely above the random chance bar. This confirms that the additional 7 features, max frequency, unique ratio, and the top-5 byte frequencies, are important for the best classification results.

Figure 3. Left and middle panels show perplexity analysis used as background context in our study. Right displays classifier accuracy for random chance, basic features, and full features.

As stated in *Methodology*, we also conducted a leave-one-feature-out analysis. Each feature was removed one at a time and accuracy was measured on the same fixed test set. Table 3 and Figure 4 present our full results in that regard.

Figure 4. Accuracy when each feature is individually removed. Green bars indicate features whose removal improves accuracy, suggesting they contribute noise. Red bars indicate features whose removal hurts accuracy, suggesting they are useful. The dashed line shows the full model baseline of 56.2%.

Feature Removed	Accuracy	Delta (%)	p-value	McNemar Significance
None (baseline)	56.2%	N/A	N/A	N/A

entropy	58.3%	+2.1%	1.000	No
mean	50.0%	-6.2%	0.450	No
variance	58.3%	+2.1%	1.000	No
max_freq	52.1%	-4.2%	0.617	No
unique_ratio	58.3%	+2.1%	1.000	No
top5_1	54.2%	-2.1%	1.000	No
top5_2	56.2%	0.0%	0.480	No
top5_3	58.3%	+2.1%	1.000	No
top5_4	62.5%	+6.2%	0.371	No
top5_5	56.2%	0.0%	0.480	No

Table 3. Leave-one-feature-out results for the 3-way classification task. Full model baseline = 56.2%. All results use McNemar's test.

As presented in the table, some patterns emerge from *Table 3* and *Figure 4*. Removing the mean byte value caused the largest accuracy drop at -6.2%, a result which was consistent across multiple runs. Max frequency shows the second largest accuracy drop, meaning these two features may provide some signal for distinguishing cipher combinations. Removing top5_4 improved accuracy by the largest margin, +6.2%, indicating that this feature could hurt classification. Removing entropy, variance, unique ratio, and top5_3 each slightly improved accuracy by +2.1%, suggesting these features contribute minimal noise.

One important distinction through McNemar's statistical test would be that none of the percentage differences produced a statistically significant result. For example, there was no significant difference between the full model and the model with mean removed (Δ Accuracy = -6.2%, McNemar $p = 0.45$). There was also no significant difference between the full model and the model with top5_4 removed (Δ Accuracy = +6.2%, McNemar $p = 0.37$). While p values vary, statistical insignificance is constant. When the same leave-one-feature-out analysis is applied to the two-way AES vs. DES task (not shown), accuracy remains near 89-93% regardless of which feature is removed.

Conclusion:

Our study investigated whether ten statistical features extracted from the ciphertext chunks can be used to classify which encryption algorithm produced them, and how the inclusion or

exclusion of these ten features affects classification accuracy. Using a Random Forest classifier trained on these features, we achieved a maximum of 61.9% accuracy on a three-way classification task and a 92.8% accuracy on a two-way task. These represent substantial improvements over the random baselines of 33.3% and 50.0% respectively.

The large accuracy gap between the two tasks suggests that meaningful differences, likely the block size difference between AES and DES, leave fingerprints as well. Our feature contribution test identified that mean byte value and max frequency appeared to be the most useful features, while several other byte frequency features appeared to contribute noise. However, McNemar's statistical test did not confirm statistical significance for any feature removal. This is likely due to the small test set size of 48 samples.

Several limitations of this study should be noted. The classifier was trained and tested on chunks from a single source text (Carroll), which means the results may not generalize to all plaintext. The test set of only 48 samples is somewhat small for McNemar's test to reliably detect significance, meaning our feature contribution findings only hypothesize differences in feature removal and accuracy. Finally, only two cipher algorithms were tested, which limits the scope of our conclusions to AES and DES specifically. Future work should expand the dataset to include more chunks and additional cipher algorithms beyond AES and DES. Additionally, testing the classifier on a greater variety of text from other sources would also help assess how well our results reflect on different inputs.

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